

Approach for Manufacturing Cost/Design Trade-Studies for Flywheels

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ABSTRACT

Different designs of advanced composite flywheels have been manufactured and tested under the U.S. Department of Energy Mechanical Energy Storage (MEST) program managed by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratories (LLNL). These concepts have included: multi-material, multi-rim, rotors with cruciform hub slats; contoured disks; multi-material-rim with twin-disk hubs, tapered thickness rotors, and hybrid disk-ring concepts. Spin tests of composite flywheels have revealed impressive energy densities and the concern of LLNL and various companies is now focussed on the transition of these experimentally produced concepts to production systems, which include surface transportations vehicles.

In order to develop cost-effective and cost-competitive composite flywheel systems (flywheel, hub, and containment). it is necessary to identify the manufacturing and other cost-drivers including test, inspection and evaluation (TI&E). A study has, therefore, been conducted to develop a methodology for analyzing the cost of these flywheel concepts which have been tested and which are now being considered for production. The manufacturing operational sequences have been specified for each flywheel and an assessment of the man-hour distribution for the manufacturing processes e.g., filament winding, has been completed. This has required interaction with the manufacturers of these flywheels.

To conduct manufacturing cost/trade studies on composite structures, it is necessary to identify general and detailed ground rules to establish manufacturing costs which can be compared on a realistic basis and also with confidence with other systems. These ground rules include composite material types, material specifications, material cost trends, data generation (recurring and non-recurring costs), support function modifiers, etc.

Utilizing the IDEF methodology (Integrated Computer-Aided manufacturing Definition method), an approach has been defined to conduct the necessary trade-studies and also includes summary tables to enable the total program cost for the flywheel, suspension and containment to be determined.

This paper reviews the initial findings of this program and discussed the science-base and engineering requirements, including manufacturing technology

developments to achieve mechanical energy storage systems with acceptable costs.